

EFFECT OF FIBER SURFACE TREATMENT ON ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION AND FRACTURE MECHANISM OF GLASS FABRIC/VINYLESTER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: This study dealt with the effect of fiber surface treatment on environmental degradation and fracture mechanism of glass woven fabric reinforced vinylester composites. Three kinds of glass fiber fabric were adopted as the reinforcements; E-glass fabrics treated by acryl-silane or epoxy-silane coupling agents and C-glass fabric treated by acryl-silane coupling agent. The specimen laminates were fabricated by stacking the same kind of fabric. Specimens were immersed in hot water, and cyclic tensile tests were conducted after immersion. In cyclic tensile test the step-stress was applied to the specimen to failure by loading-unloading process and the fracture behavior was monitored simultaneously through the AE analyses. In acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate the total AE counts in each cycle were almost constant below the applied stress of 225MPa, and after that it increased with increasing the maximum applied stress. On the other hand, the total AE counts in each cycle increased with increasing the applied stress in the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate. After immersion in hot water, the fracture mechanism never changed in the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate, however, the stress level where the AE count in each cycle began to increase was decreased with increasing the immersion time. In the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate the AE count in each cycle was reduced by immersion in water and the total AE counts to failure was extremely reduced. In this laminate the micro-damage such as interfacial debonding had already occurred before applying stress due to water immersion. C-glass fabric laminate showed the almost same tendency with the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate.

KEYWORDS: Environmental degradation, Fiber surface treatment, Tensile property, Acoustic emission

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) have often been used as structural materials under severe environment because of its superior mechanical properties and corrosion resistance. However, it is well-known that the mechanical properties of GFRP are reduced by long-term use in severe environment. Under hydrothermal environment GFRP absorbs water and it induces the chemical and physical degradation of matrix resin and fiber/matrix interface. In particular, several papers have reported that the weight change behavior under water environment was different depending on the material used¹⁻⁵. The authors have also investigated the weight change behavior of GFRP under hydrothermal environment. Our previous papers have reported that the fiber/matrix interface was degraded by water absorption and penetration and it influenced the water absorption and dissolution behavior and the mechanical properties⁶⁻⁹. Therefore it is important to investigate the influence of interfacial property on environmental degradation of GFRP in order to improve the long-term durability of GFRP under severe environment.

Interfacial property is significantly influenced by the surface treatment of fiber. Many papers have reported the relation between silane treatment of fiber and mechanical properties. However, few papers have studied the influence of silane treatment on environmental degradation of GFRP. From this reason, we have investigated the influence of silane treatment of the glass fiber on mechanical properties and environmental degradation¹⁰. Poor interfacial adhesion induces the serious reduction in mechanical properties after hydrothermal aging, while strong interfacial adhesion can sustain the good mechanical properties. However, the actual stress level is not clear for practical application under hydrothermal environment.

From this background, this study dealt with the influence of fiber surface treatment on environmental degradation and fracture mechanism of glass woven fabric reinforced vinylester composites. In addition, the influence of chemical composition of glass fiber on environmental degradation was also investigated. The laminates were immersed in hot water and the loading-unloading tensile tests were performed with monitoring acoustic emission in order to investigate the influence of fiber on fracture behavior after environmental immersion.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials used were plain woven glass fabric as reinforcement and vinylester resin as matrix. In order to discuss the influence of glass fiber type on fracture behavior after environmental exposure, E-glass fiber and C-glass fiber fabrics were adopted as the reinforcement. In E-glass fabric, two kinds of silane treatment; acryl-silane and epoxy-silane, were adopted. Acryl-silane coupling agent is suitable in chemical reaction for vinylester resin, while epoxy-silane coupling agent is usually suitable for epoxy resin and not suitable for vinylester resin. C-glass fabric is treated by acryl-silane coupling agent. By stacking 12 plies of the same fiber fabrics, three kinds of laminates were fabricated by hand lay-up method.

In order to discuss the effects of environmental exposure on fracture behavior of the laminates, specimens were immersed in distilled water at 95°C by using temperature controlled water bath. Immersion times were 0, 5, 10, 50 and 100 hours. After the fixed periods of immersion the surface of the specimen was wiped out by paper towel to remove drops of water before the mechanical testing.

After environmental immersion, static tensile test was performed. In order to discuss the reliable stress level for actual application, the maximum applied stress was increased step by step to final failure as schematically shown in Figure 1. The applied maximum stress was increased 25MPa step and minimum stress level was fixed at 5MPa. Static tensile test was performed by Instron type universal testing machine (AGS-1000B, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan) at a constant crosshead speed of 1mm/min in air at room temperature. During tensile test, acoustic emission (AE) from the specimen was monitored simultaneously in order to discuss the effects of environmental immersion and fiber type on fracture behavior. AE signal was monitored by 7600 series AE instrument (NF Corporation, Japan). Two AE transducers with the resonant frequency of 140 kHz were attached onto the specimen as shown in Figure 2, and AE was monitored with the total gain of 50dB and 70dB (different in each transducer) and the threshold of 100mV.

Fig.1 Static tensile test with s

Fig.2 Experimental set-up of tensile test

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.3 shows the changes of the tensile strength of each laminates after the immersion in hot water. In this figure AS and ES correspond the acryl-silane treated and epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminates respectively. In virgin specimens, the tensile strength depended on the chemical composition of glass fiber. The tensile strength of the C-glass laminate was 25% lower than that of the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate. However, the effect of silane treatment of fiber was poor in virgin specimens. After water immersion, the tensile strength of the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate decreased gradually 50 hours immersion and gradually approached the constant value in further immersion. The strength reduction after 100 hours immersion was about 25%. The strength reduction behavior of C-glass laminate was almost the same tendency with the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate in spite of the difference in the initial strength. On the other hand, the silane treatment of fiber greatly affected the strength reduction due to water immersion. The strength of epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate decreased significantly after immersion and it reached about 60% of the virgin specimen after 100 hours immersion.

In order to discuss the mechanism and main cause of strength reduction, loading-unloading

Fig.3 Changes of tensile strength after immersion in hot water.

Fig.4 Stress-strain history of the C-glass laminate under cyclic loading with the AE monitoring.

tensile test and simultaneous acoustic emission (AE) monitoring were performed. Figs.4-6 show the stress histories and changes of AE event count and maximum amplitude of virgin specimens for each laminates. In these figures AE event count indicates the accumulation of event count in each loading-unloading cycle and AE maximum amplitude indicates the maximum amplitude of event at each time. In the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate the cumulative AE event count at each cycle was almost constant to maximum applied stress of 225MPa, and it gradually increased with increasing the maximum applied stress. From this result, the laminate did not have serious damage at applied stress below 225MPa. Same tendency in the cumulative AE event count appeared in the C-glass laminate, however, the stress level without serious damage was 150MPa. In the C-glass laminate serious damage occurred at lower stress level than the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate, and it brought the lower tensile strength of the C-glass laminate. In the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate, AE evolution was quite different from the acryl-silane treated laminate. The cumulative AE event count at each cycle continuously increased with increasing the maximum applied stress, and the number of cumulative event count was much higher than the acryl-silane treated laminate. These results suggested that the fracture behavior depended on the fiber surface treatment. In the laminate with poor interfacial adhesion (epoxy-silane treated laminate), AE event with low and middle range amplitude occurred remarkably. Such events might correspond to the fracture of fiber/matrix interface.

Figs.7 and 8 show the stress histories and changes of AE event count and maximum amplitude of the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminates immersed for 10 and 100 hours. At low stress level the cumulative AE count in each stress cycle kept almost constant even after 100 hours immersion, and such tendency was the same with the virgin specimen. However, the stress where the number of cumulative AE count began to increase gradually decreased with increasing the immersion time. In the 100 hours immersed specimen the number of cumulative AE count came to increase over 175MPa, while it came to increase over 225MPa in the virgin specimen. As shown in Fig.3, the

Fig.7 Stress history and changes of AE event count and maximum amplitude of the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate immersed for 10 hours.

tensile strength reduction of the 100 hours immersed specimen was about 25%, and such values were same with the tensile strength reduction due to water immersion. The main fracture at middle stress level was the debonding between fiber and matrix in weft fiber bundle, and it was related to the adhesion between fiber and matrix. Therefore it is considered that the main cause of the strength reduction in the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate was the adhesion strength reduction between fiber and matrix. This phenomenon was also reflected to the maximum amplitude of AE event. As the immersion time came to be longer, the number of AE event with high amplitude, which is related

to the fiber fracture, decreased. This also suggested the adhesion strength reduction between fiber and matrix.

Figs.9 and 10 show the stress histories and changes of AE event count and maximum amplitude of the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminates immersed for 10 and 100 hours. In the epoxy-silane treated E-glass virgin laminate, AE event with middle range amplitude often occurred, while it gradually decreased with increasing the immersion time as shown in Figs. 9 and 10. In general, AE event with middle range amplitude is related to the fracture between fiber and matrix. Therefore the results shown in Figs. 9 and 10 indicated that the fracture between fiber and matrix came not to occur as the immersion time became longer. In these laminates it is considered that the interfacial adhesion

Fig.9 Stress history and changes of AE event count and maximum amplitude of the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate immersed for 10 hours.

was poor even without water immersion, and such interface is easily attacked by the water penetration into the interface. As a result, the interfacial adhesion became very poor due to water immersion, and the fracture between fiber and matrix had already occurred due to water penetration into the interface. Such degradation between fiber and matrix brought the significant strength reduction in the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate.

Figs.11 and 12 show the stress histories and changes of AE event count and maximum amplitude of the C-glass laminates immersed for 10 and 100 hours. In the C-glass laminate, the fibers

Fig.11 Stress history and changes of AE event count and maximum amplitude of the C-glass laminate immersed for 10 hours.

were treated by the acryl-silane coupling agent, and this surface treatment was the same with the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate. However, the changes of AE characteristics due to water immersion in the C-glass laminate were different from the E-glass laminate. In the C-glass laminate the stress where the number of cumulative AE count began to increase did not change due to water immersion. In the laminate immersed for 100 hours the increase of the cumulative AE event never occurred just before the final failure. This result might suggest that the degradation of the fiber/matrix interface did not occur in the C-glass laminate, and the main cause of the tensile strength reduction might be different from the E-glass laminate. In the C-glass laminate the durability against the damage accumulation decreased due to water immersion, which was related to the strength reduction (toughness reduction) of the matrix resin. Therefore it is considered that the strength reduction mechanism due to water immersion is different depending on not only the surface treatment but also the fiber type.

From the above-mentioned results, the mechanism of the strength reduction due to water immersion is summarized as follows. In the E-glass fiber laminate the surface treatment of the fiber is sensitive to the strength reduction under hydrothermal environment. Poor interfacial adhesion brings the degradation of the interface by aging (without applying the stress), and it induces the tensile strength reduction. Even in the laminate with good adhesion at the interface the degradation of the interface gradually occurs and it brings the gradual tensile strength reduction. On the other hand, the tensile strength reduction in the C-glass fiber laminate is mainly caused by the degradation of the matrix without the degradation of the interface.

CONCLUSION

This study dealt with the effect of fiber surface treatment and fiber type on environmental degradation and fracture mechanism of glass woven fabric reinforced vinylester composite laminates. Three kinds of glass fiber fabric were adopted as the reinforcements; E-glass fabrics treated by acryl-silane or epoxy-silane coupling agents and C-glass fabric treated by acryl-silane coupling agent. In acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate the total AE counts in each cycle were almost constant below the applied stress of 225MPa, and after that it increased with increasing the maximum applied stress. On the other hand, the total AE counts in each cycle increased with increasing the applied stress in the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate. After immersion in hot water, the fracture mechanism never changed in the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate, however, the stress level where the AE count in each cycle began to increase was decreased with increasing the immersion time. In the epoxy-silane treated E-glass laminate the AE count in each cycle was reduced by immersion in water and the total AE counts to failure was extremely reduced. In this laminate the micro-damage such as interfacial debonding had already occurred before applying stress due to water immersion. C-glass fabric laminate showed the almost same tendency with the acryl-silane treated E-glass laminate, however, the stress level where the AE count in each cycle began to increase never changed even after immersion in hot water. The fiber surface treatment was much more sensitive to the degradation mechanism change than the fiber type.

REFERENCES

1. A. C. Loos, G. S. Springer, B. A. Sanders and R. W. Tung, "Moisture absorption of polyester-E glass composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 14(1980), 142-154.
2. C. H. Shen and G. S. Springer, "Effects of moisture and temperature on the tensile strength of composite materials", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 11(1977), 2-16.
3. C. H. Shen and G. S. Springer, "Environmental effects on the elastic moduli of composite materials", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 11(1977), 250-264.
4. R. Gopalan, R. M. V. G. K. Rao and M. V. V. Murthy, "Diffusion studies on advanced fibre hybrid composites", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 5(1986), 51-61.
5. B. Ellis and M. S. Found, "The effects of water absorption on a polyester/chopped strand mat laminate", *Composites*, 14(1983), 237-243.
6. T. Morii, H. Hamada, Z. Maekawa, T. Tanimoto, T. Hirano and K. Kiyosumi, "Weight changes of a randomly oriented GRP panel in hot water", *Composites Science and Technology*, 49(1993), 209-216.
7. T. Morii, H. Hamada, Z. Maekawa, T. Tanimoto, T. Hirano, K. Kiyosumi and T. Tsujii, "Weight changes of the fibre/matrix interface in GRP panels immersed in hot water", *Composites Science and Technology*, 50(1994), 373-380.
8. T. Morii, H. Hamada, Z. Maekawa, T. Tanimoto, T. Hirano and K. Kiyosumi, "Fracture and acoustic emission characteristics of glass fiber reinforced plastics panel in hot water", *Polymer Composites*, 15(1994), 206-216.
9. T. Morii, N. Ikuta, K. Kiyosumi and H. Hamada, "Weight-changes of the interphase in hygrothermally aged FRP: Consideration of debonding", *Composites Science and Technology*, 57(1997), 985-990.

10. T. Morii, N. Ikuta and H. Hamada, "Influence of water immersion on mechanical properties of glass fabric/epoxy laminates with different fiber surface treatment", *Journal of Society of Materials Science, Japan (in Japanese)*, 46(1997), 309-314.